

e-ISSN: 3048-6440

Volume 03 Issue 01
Jan-Apr, 2026

***Corresponding
Author: V R Srividhya,**
Assistant Professor,
Department of CSE, RV
Institute of Technology
and Management,
Bangalore, India

Machine Learning and Complex Event Processing: Shaping the Future of Smart Agriculture

*Kishan Praveen Rao¹, Krati Mahajan², Mahesh M
G³, Manya Shree⁴, V R Srividhya^{5*}*

*^{1,2,3,4} Student, ⁵Assistant Professor, Department of CSE,
RV Institute of Technology and Management, Bangalore,
India*

ABSTRACT

The incorporation of advanced technologies in Smart Agriculture has opened new possibilities for enhancing productivity and sustainability. Among these, Machine Learning (ML) has been widely adopted for crop recommendation and yield prediction by analyzing historical agricultural data, achieving impressive prediction accuracies with various algorithms. However, most existing systems are static and do not adapt to real-time changes in environmental conditions. This paper surveys recent advancements in ML-based crop recommendation systems and explores the emerging role of Complex Event Processing (CEP) in enabling real-time decision-making in Smart Agriculture. CEP engines can analyze continuous streams of sensor data to detect critical patterns such as drought, nutrient stress, triggering alerts or adjustments to crop choices. We discuss how the fusion of ML and CEP offers a dynamic and intelligent decision support system (DSS) for farmers, enabling context-aware recommendations that respond to real-time field conditions. This survey identifies existing gaps in integrating streaming data with contextual decision-making in agriculture and highlights the potential of combining CEP and ML as a promising direction for future research.

Keywords: *Smart Agriculture, Complex Event Processing (CEP), Machine Learning (ML), Decision Support System (DSS)*

1. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays a vital role in global prosperity, food security, and economic growth. However, traditional farming systems continue to face critical challenges, especially in countries like India, where cultivation remains one of the major occupations. Small farms dominate the Indian agricultural landscape, with over 75% of landholdings being less than 5 acres. Despite agriculture accounting for 60.46% of the total land use in India, only 45.6% of that land is irrigated, making the majority of farming activities dependent on rainfall. This sector supports the nutritional needs of over 1.2 billion people, yet continues to suffer from issues such as poor crop selection, low yield, and farmer debt, which have led to widespread disillusionment - nearly 48% of Indian farmers do not want their children to continue farming, citing uncertainty and financial losses [1].

Smart agriculture, or smart farming, represents a significant shift from traditional methods, aiming to transform farming into a more connected, efficient, and sustainable practice. The key goals of smart agriculture include boosting productivity, enhancing efficiency, optimizing resource management (such as water, fertilizer, and energy), reducing environmental impact, and building resilience to climate challenges [2, 3]. At the heart of this revolution is the use of technology, which facilitates a more intelligent, data-driven approach to farming.

Machine Learning (ML), a subfield of Artificial Intelligence (AI), enables computers to learn from data and improve performance without being explicitly programmed [4]. It employs computational techniques to identify patterns and trends within datasets, allowing systems to make predictions or informed decisions. In agriculture, ML

algorithms support tasks such as pattern recognition, outcome forecasting, and decision-making-helping to recommend optimal farming practices, detect diseases, and manage resources more efficiently [5, 6].

Complex Event Processing (CEP) is a methodology that facilitates the real-time analysis of streaming event data, allowing systems to detect and respond to significant occurrences as they happen. It encompasses a set of concepts and techniques designed to continuously process incoming events, extract meaningful information, and identify patterns or anomalies in real time [4, 7]. In agriculture, CEP enables the monitoring of sensor data streams to detect critical field conditions such as nutrient imbalances, environmental stress, or drought events [8]. CEP is particularly effective at handling high volumes of data with low latency, making it a top technology for Internet of Things (IoT) environments [9].

Real-time Decision Support Systems (DSS) are intelligent systems that analyze real-time data to offer timely, context-aware guidance. In agriculture, they can be used to process historical and live sensor data, helping farmers make informed crop decisions [4, 5]. This survey explores recent advancements in these technologies, highlighting trends, integration challenges, and future research directions.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

ML-Based Approaches

Crop selection and yield prediction Using ML Techniques [1] compared multiple ML models, such as Random Forest and Decision Trees, to deliver accurate crop selection and yield forecasting using soil nutrients and meteorological parameters. While achieving high accuracy for both Crop Recommendation as well as Yield

Prediction, the system omits some key variables like wind speed and salinity, limiting predictive robustness. Also, the author mentions that using Deep Learning models might improve the efficiency.

Enhanced Maize Cultivation: IoT Based Precision Agriculture System [2] introduced an IoT-based system for maize cultivation using a rover and dew nodes. This data is analyzed by Machine Learning models (SVM, Random Forest) to predict soil health and automate irrigation based on moisture thresholds.

Enhancing Agricultural Productivity: A Machine Learning Approach to Crop Recommendations [3] compared nine ML algorithms and identified Random Forest as the most accurate for crop recommendation. While powerful, their model currently lacks real-time feedback mechanisms, a critical aspect for adapting to environmental volatility.

A Decision Support System for Crop Recommendation Using Machine Learning Classification Algorithms [5] developed a mobile-based DSS that compares thirteen ML algorithms, using cloud-based datasets and GPS data to recommend optimal crops for Indian farmers. Their use of SMOTE and SGDC resulted in highly accurate predictions, though they do not yet integrate real-time sensor data.

Crop Recommendation System using Machine Learning [6] evaluated several supervised ML algorithms to recommend crops across India based on soil and weather attributes. Gaussian Naïve Bayes and Random Forest achieved high accuracy, making their framework a strong static recommendation engine, albeit without real-time adaptation.

Review—Machine Learning Techniques in Wire- less Sensor Network Based Precision Agriculture [10] provided an extensive

review of ML models applied in Wireless Sensor Network (WSN)-based precision farming. They also introduced a case study prototype that integrates real-time sensor data with ML models via a mobile application, enabling actionable insights for water usage and soil monitoring, strongly supporting real-time DSS frameworks.

Smart Farming: Crop Recommendation using Machine Learning with Challenges and Future Ideas [15] benchmarked seven ML algorithms and attained near-perfect accuracy in crop recommendation. Their acknowledgment of real-world agricultural constraints-like pests and water scarcity-makes their framework suitable for integration with CEP systems to enable responsive decision-making.

Artificial Neural Networks for Soil Quality and Crop Yield Prediction using Machine Learning [16] proposed a software-driven model using Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) to predict soil quality, crop suitability, and fertilizer recommendations based on pH and nutrient data. While the approach is cost-effective and fast, the paper does not present specific numerical performance metrics for its own model's outcomes.

Design of an integrated climatic assessment indicator (ICAI) for wheat production: A case study in Jiangsu Province, China [17] created an Integrated Climatic Assessment Indicator (ICAI) using Support Vector Machines and Random Forest to classify wheat yield under changing climate conditions. Their focus on climatic sensitivity analysis makes the model useful for long-term yield forecasting, though it currently lacks phenological adaptability.

Transforming Agriculture: A Synergistic Approach Integrating Topology with Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for Sustainable and Data Driven Practice [18] proposed a novel framework

combining topological spatial data with ML for proactive pest control, yield optimization, and targeted irrigation. Various ML algorithms were customized and applied for specific agricultural jobs, including optimizing resource allocation, forecasting crop yield, identifying illness, and classifying crops.

CEP-Based Approaches

Complex Event Processing system for IoT greenhouse [8] plays a vital role in real-time monitoring and alert generation by detecting patterns across data streams, proposed a CEP system tailored for IoT greenhouses, focusing on automata-based rule engines to manage environmental control and early warnings. Their modular Event Processing Agent (EPA) design ensures interpretability and adaptability.

Complex event processing over distributed probabilistic event streams [9] introduced a Distributed Probabilistic Complex Event Processing (DPCEP) architecture to handle uncertainty in large-scale IoT environments. Their extension of the SASE method allows CEP to operate over probabilistic event streams with confidence scoring, a critical feature for noisy agricultural sensor data.

Complex Event Processing [11] presents a foundational overview of CEP, drawing heavily from David Luckham's work. It explores formal event modeling, real-time pattern matching using languages like NFA^b and RAPIDE-EPL, and highlights applications in RFID, finance, and industrial systems. The paper also discusses challenges such as uncertainty in event materialization and emphasizes efficient stream processing.

Siddhi: A Second Look at Complex Event Processing Architectures [13] critically analyses existing Complex Event Processing (CEP) engine designs. It proposes and implements improvements in

a new engine, Siddhi, by adopting stream processing style pipelines and multithreading. Siddhi's performance, especially for pattern matching, significantly surpasses that of other open-source CEP engines like Esper.

Hybrid or Integrated Systems

It's a Machine Learning world: no future for Complex Event Processing? [4] provided a reflective analysis of CEP and ML in Early Warning Systems and advocated for hybrid models. They highlighted the challenges of unsupervised learning in CEP rule generation and emphasized the importance of integrating ML to automate and adapt CEP logic in real-world systems like agriculture.

Determination of Rule Patterns in Complex Event Processing Using Machine Learning Techniques [7] addresses the challenge of manually defining complex event processing (CEP) rule patterns for real-time analysis of extensive streaming sensor and RFID data. It proposes to automate this process by integrating machine learning (ML) techniques, specifically rule-based classifiers, to derive these patterns.

Integrating Complex Event Processing and Machine Learning: An Intelligent Architecture for Detecting IoT Security Attacks [12] presents an intelligent architecture combining Complex Event Processing (CEP) and Machine Learning (ML) for real-time detection of IoT security threats. Tested in a hospital network, it accurately detects known and unknown attacks like Mirai with low false positives. The lightweight design suits resource-limited devices like Raspberry Pi, outperforming traditional security methods.

An automatic unsupervised complex event processing rules generation architecture for real-time IoT attacks detection [14], introduces an architecture designed to automatically generate Complex Event

Processing (CEP) rules for real-time detection and classification of IoT network attacks. This is achieved without the need for manual definition by a domain expert, employing an unsupervised approach. The proposed system integrates Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) and Mahalanobis distance to model normal network traffic and identify anomalies.

Grand Challenge: StreamLearner – Distributed Incremental Machine Learning on Event Streams [19] proposes StreamLearner, a distributed Complex Event Processing (CEP) system designed for Machine Learning (ML)-enabled complex event detection on real-time event streams. It integrates online ML training and inference to detect fuzzy patterns and improve pattern recognition accuracy through incremental model training. Its data-parallel architecture allows dynamically scaling resources for low-latency, high-throughput processing, exemplified by anomaly detection in smart factories.

Automatic Rule Updating based on Machine Learning in Complex Event Processing [20] addresses the limitation of static, manually defined rules in Complex Event Processing (CEP), which are hard to adapt in dynamic environments. It proposes an automatic rule updating method using Machine Learning (ML), inspired by Support Vector Machines (SVM), to dynamically learn and adapt to changing conditions. This enhances rule portability by replacing abnormal rules from data, useful in smart traffic and city contexts.

3. BACKGROUND AND KEY CONCEPTS

Understanding the foundational concepts of smart agriculture and the technologies that enable it is crucial for appreciating the potential and implementation of advanced systems like those integrating Complex

Event Processing (CEP) and Machine Learning (ML). This section provides an overview of these key concepts.

Smart Agriculture

Smart agriculture introduces transformative changes in farming by integrating technologies such as IoT sensors, drones, smart irrigation, and satellite imagery [2, 5]. These tools enhance crop productivity, optimize the use of resources like water and fertilizers, and reduce the risk of crop loss. Smart farming supports informed decision-making by considering local factors such as climate, soil composition, and water availability-enabling more personalized crop recommendations [5]. This shift from traditional methods is essential in addressing modern challenges like limited arable land, inefficient practices, and the growing global demand for food [3]. In India, where a significant portion of the population depends on small-scale agriculture, smart farming plays a critical role in improving sustainability, profitability, and farmer welfare.

The Internet of Things (IoT) is central to smart agriculture, connecting various sensors that monitor key environmental and soil conditions. These sensors collect real-time data on parameters such as temperature, humidity, pH, and soil nutrients, which are transmitted wirelessly to central systems-even in remote areas. This data is visualized on dashboards, aiding timely decision-making [2, 5, 10]. Precision agriculture builds on this data-driven approach to optimize the use of inputs like water, pesticides, and fertilizers. It improves efficiency, reduces environmental impact, and enhances yield through techniques such as crop recommendation, yield prediction, and smart resource management [5, 10].

Complex Event Processing (CEP)

Complex Event Processing (CEP) is a powerful method for real-time analysis of

event streams, designed to detect significant patterns or “situations of interest” by collecting, correlating, and analyzing simple, low-level events [7]. Built on Event-Driven Architecture (EDA), CEP enables systems to respond proactively by triggering actions based on event relationships like time, causality, and aggregation [11]. It allows for the detection of complex events that may not be directly observable, enabling timely decision-making. The basic architecture of a CEP engine is illustrated in Figure 1. With low latency and high throughput, modern CEP engines can process millions of events per second, making them ideal for high-volume, data-intensive environments like smart agriculture [4]. By transforming raw sensor data into actionable insights, CEP supports Early Warning Systems (EWS) and Decision Support Systems (DSS), empowering users to monitor dynamic situations and intervene effectively [4, 7, and 11].

CEP operates on continuous event streams collected from diverse sources such as IoT sensors, log files, and networks [7, 11]. These simple events are preprocessed and analyzed using predefined rules to generate complex events. Rules, written in Event Processing Languages (e.g., SiddhiQL), define the logic for filtering, aggregating, and correlating events [12-14]. However, manually crafting rules is often impractical due to data volume and variability, prompting research into ML-based rule automation [14]. Core strength of CEP lies in pattern detection-identifying meaningful sequences, temporal constraints, anomalies, and logical combinations (e.g., sequencing, negation, and disjunction) [7]. CEP engines often use Nondeterministic Finite Automata (NFA) to efficiently model these patterns, ensuring real-time responsiveness and scalability across dynamic, data-rich environments [9, 11, and 13].

Fig.1:-Basic CEP architecture

Machine Learning in Agriculture

Machine Learning (ML) plays a transformative role in smart agriculture by analyzing historical and real-time data to support better decision-making. It enhances sustainability and productivity through predictive insights in key areas like crop recommendation, yield prediction, and environmental analysis. ML-powered Decision Support Systems (DSS) use these capabilities to provide timely, context-aware guidance based on real-world sensor data and historical patterns [2-5].

Crop recommendation uses ML algorithms such as Random Forest, SVM, and XGBoost to identify the most suitable crops based on parameters like soil nutrients (NPK, pH) and climate (temperature, humidity, rainfall). Figure 2 presents an overview of most used machine learning algorithms. These systems provide personalized suggestions that improve farm productivity and

sustainability [3, 5, 6, and 15]. Yield prediction, on the other hand, leverages data like land use, fertilizer consumption, weather conditions, and past yields to forecast output. Techniques like Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), regression models, and ensemble methods are commonly used for this task [1, 2, 5, 10, 16].

Lastly, soil and climate analysis are essential for assessing environmental suitability and detecting early signs of stress or nutrient deficiency [16-18]. Data from soil and weather sensors, remote sensing tools, and historical records are processed using ML methods like ANN, SVM, and clustering algorithms [10, 16]. These insights help farmers optimize resources and react proactively to field changes. Together, these applications form the backbone of smart agriculture, making farming more efficient, data-driven, and resilient [2, 6].

Fig.2:-Most Common ML Algorithms

Integration of ML and CEP

The integration of Machine Learning (ML) and Complex Event Processing (CEP) presents a powerful synergy for smart systems, particularly in dynamic and data-rich environments like IoT, crisis management, smart factories, and precision agriculture [4, 8, 12, 19]. CEP excels at handling high-velocity data streams with ultra-low latency, but its reliance on manually defined rules limits adaptability [7]. ML addresses this by automating rule generation, enabling systems to learn and adapt to new patterns from historical data [4, 7]. This combination enhances real-time pattern detection, anomaly identification, and decision-making, especially in environments where static rules fall short, such as detecting unknown threats or subtle anomalies in large datasets [4, 12, 20].

Applications of this ML-CEP synergy span several domains. In IoT security, ML aids in dynamic rule creation while CEP ensures timely intrusion detection on

resource-constrained devices [12, 14]. In crisis management and early warning systems, their hybrid use supports fast, informed responses to unstructured and evolving data [4]. In smart factories, CEP engines integrated with ML perform real-time anomaly detection in sensor data [19]. In precision agriculture, ML models analyze environmental data for crop decisions [2], while CEP monitors for deviations in greenhouse conditions to trigger timely alerts [8]. Together, they enable adaptive, intelligent systems that go beyond static analytics toward automated context-aware interventions.

4. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Tables 1. And 2. Provide a detailed comparative overview of the existing approaches. Table 1. summarizes the performance of various Machine Learning (ML) models applied to agricultural use cases. It shows that while ML offers high predictive accuracy and the ability to learn from historical data, it often requires large amounts of labeled data and may not handle real-time changes effectively.

Table 1:-Comparative Performance Analysis of Reviewed ML Works in the Field of Agriculture

Ref. No	Proposed Framework	Dataset Used	Performance Analysis	Discussions
1.	ML-based crop selection and yield prediction framework	Crop Recommendation & Yield Prediction Datasets - Kaggle	Algorithms: Random Forest, Naive Bayes, SVM, KNN, Decision Tree, Gradient Boosting. Among these, Random Forest achieved highest accuracy (99.29%) for crop recommendation and Decision Tree achieved highest (95.93%) accuracy for yield prediction.	Focused on regional prediction; lacks detailed metrics but supports ML utility for crop planning.
2.	IoT based Precision Agriculture System	Real-time data collected through sensors on the field	Ensemble of SVM and Random Forest used.	Combines ML predictions and real-time control; practical but lacks model specificity and is crop-specific.

3.	Machine Learning Approach to Crop Recommendations	Kaggle archives - Food and Agriculture Council of India	Algorithms: LR, SVM, KNN, DT, RF, BG, AB, GB, ET. RF achieved highest accuracy (99.3%).	Enriches accuracy and relevance, lacks real-time feedback mechanisms.
5.	Decision Support System for Crop Recommendation using classifiers	Historical dataset from multiple sources	Algorithms: LR, DT, KNN, SVC, RF, GB, Bagged Tree, XGBoost, AdaBoost, Cat Boost, HGB, Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGDC), Multinomial NB. Before SMOTE, SGDC accuracy = 0.95; after SMOTE, SGDC accuracy = 1.00.	Accurate, data-driven recommendations based on season and area name boost yields, but they depend on high-quality data and lack real-time sensor integration.
6.	ML-based crop recommendation model	Crop recommendation dataset - Kaggle	Algorithms: LR, DT, RF, KNN, NB, SVM, Neural Network. Among these, Random Forest achieved highest accuracy (99.545%).	Scalable and easily adapted to new data and regions.
15.	Machine Learning based Crop Recommendation System	Crop Recommendation Dataset - Kaggle	Algorithms: Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), Gaussian Naïve Bayes (GNB). Based on the results provided, the model performs great with Validation Accuracy Score of 99.3%.	Can enhance the productivity and profitability by using this technique.
16.	Artificial Neural Networks for Soil Quality and Crop Yield Prediction	3 datasets - pH, Crop dataset and fertilizer dataset	ANN: Back propagation Networking. Accuracy is said to increase with the increase in the number of hidden layers as well as input parameters.	Presents a software-based ANN model for predicting soil quality, crop suitability, and fertilizer needs, offering timely guidance to farmers. However, it relies heavily on quality datasets and lacks real-world validation details.
17.	Integrated Climatic Assessment Indicator (ICAI) for wheat production	China Meteorological Assimilation Driving Datasets - Cold and Arid Regions Science Data Center at	Algorithms: SVM, RF. Among SVM and RF, Random Forest achieved highest accuracy for all the 3 regions - North: 92.31%, Middle: 67.86%, South: 75%.	High spatial and temporal prediction accuracies; Agro-climatic effects are continuous concerns at present and in the future.

		Lanzhou		
18.	Synergistic Approach Integrating Topology with Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning	Dataset created by combining information from several sources, including: Satellite images, Real-time sensor networks, Public databases.	Algorithms: RF, SVR, BPNN with hyperparameter optimisation and Clustering Algorithms, CNN and RNN. The highest R ² achieved is 0.69 by the SVR algorithm when utilizing the Grid Search optimization strategy.	Presents a novel AI-ML-topology integration for improved agricultural decision-making. However, limited empirical metrics and high sensitivity to hyperparameter tuning restrict broader validation.

Table 2. Compares Complex Event Processing (CEP), ML, and integrated ML+CEP systems. CEP is strong in real-time pattern detection but relies on manually defined rules, which limits flexibility. ML, on the other hand, is

adaptive and data-driven but lacks real-time responsiveness. Integrated approaches aim to combine the best of both but come with architectural complexity and integration challenges.

Table 2:-Comparative Analysis of CEP, ML and Integrated Approaches

Feature/Aspect	Complex Event Processing (CEP)	Machine Learning (ML)	Integrated Approaches (ML + CEP)
Definition	Focuses on processing events in real-time to identify complex patterns [4].	Enables computers to learn and improve from large data to make predictions [4, 6].	Combines CEP and ML to create adaptive and intelligent systems [12, 14].
Primary Goal	Detect and respond to key events in real-time [4].	Model patterns to predict or classify future data [4], [6].	Automate rule generation and make adaptive decisions in real-time [4, 14].
Rule/Model Generation	Uses manually defined rules by domain experts [14].	Trains on historical data to generate models [3].	ML updates CEP rules or generates patterns dynamically [14].
Key Advantage	Low latency event detection; scalable for big data streams [4].	Uncovers hidden patterns and adapts to changes [4].	Detects novel events with real-time + predictive synergy [12, 14].
Key Limitation	Manual rules are difficult to update in dynamic settings [7].	Needs labeled data, performance may vary [4].	Complex architecture and ethical/interpretability issues.
Example Application	IoT attack detection [12, 14], fraud monitoring, home care [11].	Crop prediction [5], soil quality [16], financial forecasting [4].	Unsupervised IoT defense [14], smart agriculture, pollution tracking [5].

This comparison highlights that many existing approaches lack adaptive, real-time decision-making capabilities, indicating a gap that future research can focus on.

5. RESEARCH GAPS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Upon meticulously screening through several notable works and advancements introduced in the field of agriculture - particularly including Machine Learning, Complex Event Processing, and several other integrated systems, we came across a couple of research gaps that encouraged us to develop upgrades that will be highly enriching in the domain of smart agriculture research, which include:

- We observed a lack of proper real-time, integrated systems in the field of agriculture. Many Complex Event Processing (CEP) systems still rely on static rules and struggle to adapt dynamically based on real-time feedback [14].
- The act of agriculture is well-diversified, with numerous crops depending on numerous factors. In such instances, scalability and deployment becomes a challenge, as most systems are tailored for just a few crops or environmental needs. This undoubtedly limits the scope for optimal enhancement [1,6].
- We believe that building systems should be farmer centric. There is a noticeable lack of decision-support tools that are simple and intuitive for farmers to understand and use effectively [5].
- The gap between ideas proposed on paper and the implementations done on farmland is vivid and visible. We

need to develop a system that reaches out to the right set of target users.

For any study being conducted, the best achievement desired is that it should address real-world problems and provide optimal solutions as promised. Taking special care of the above-stated notion, we propose the following future enhancements, which are well-crafted and suggested to best serve the concerns laid out:

- Future research should focus on developing hybrid systems that integrate Complex Event Processing with Machine Learning for automatic, unsupervised, and dynamic generation and continuous adaptation of rules in response to evolving environmental and system conditions, especially in the field of precision agriculture [14].
- Most agricultural ML systems still rely on traditional algorithms, with deep learning, especially unsupervised methods, remaining under-explored. Future research should focus on leveraging deep learning to uncover complex patterns in sensor data for more adaptive and scalable decision-making.
- Agricultural yields are influenced by dynamic factors like weather, soil, humidity, and nutrients, which vary across time and location. However, existing datasets and models often lack support for a wide variety of crops and farming contexts. Developing real-time frameworks with broader crop coverage remains a key area for future advancement.
- Future research should consider the economic and environmental impacts of these advanced agricultural

systems, and explore their ethical and societal implications, such as privacy, bias, and fairness [6]. Integrating farmers' professional knowledge and feedback loops into system design will also be crucial for refining and enhancing recommendations [3].

6. CONCLUSION

In summary, this survey emphasizes the growing importance of intelligent, data-driven systems in modern agriculture. Machine Learning (ML) has proven effective in analyzing historical crop data to offer accurate and personalized crop recommendations, while Complex Event Processing (CEP) excels at monitoring real-time sensor data for early detection of anomalies. However, most existing approaches treat these technologies independently, limiting their adaptability to real-time field conditions.

This survey identifies a promising research direction: the integration of ML and CEP into real-time Decision Support Systems, where predictive models recommend crops and CEP monitors real-time or simulated data streams to trigger alerts. Such synergy can transform static outputs into adaptive decisions. By combining prediction with real-time alerts, the system helps farmers make quicker, smarter, and more sustainable decisions, marking a step forward in the evolution of precision agriculture.

REFERENCES

1. Kommina, S. B., Chandra Sekhar, A. V. N., Unnava, S., Rao, G. N., & Vinay, T. (2024). Crop selection and yield prediction using ML techniques. *Periodico di Mineralogia*, 93(6), 169–182.
2. Roy, S., Kundu, S., & Bhowmik, T. (2025). Enhanced maize cultivation: IoT based precision agriculture system. In *Proceedings of the 2025 8th International Conference on Electronics, Materials Engineering & Nano-Technology (IEMENTech)* (pp. 1–6). IEEE.
3. Prity, S., Hasan, M. M., Saif, S. H., Hossain, M. M., Bhuiyan, S. H., Islam, M. A., & Lavlu, M. T. H. (2024). Enhancing agricultural productivity: A machine learning approach to crop recommendations. *Human-Centric Intelligent Systems*, 4(4), 497–510.
4. Barthe-Delanoë, A.-M. (2024). It's a machine learning world: No future for complex event processing? In *Proceedings of the International ISCRAM Conference*.
5. Senapaty, M. K., Ray, A., & Padhy, N. (2024). A decision support system for crop recommendation using machine learning classification algorithms. *Agriculture*, 14(8), 1256.
6. Dahiphale, P., Shinde, P., Patil, K., & Dahiphale, V. (2023). Smart farming: Crop recommendation using machine learning with challenges and future ideas. *Periodico di Mineralogia*, 00(0), 1–11.
7. Mehdiyeva, N., Krumeich, J., Enke, D., Werth, D., & Loos, P. (2015). Determination of rule patterns in complex event processing using machine learning techniques. *Procedia Computer Science*, 61, 395–401.
8. Jia, Y., Huang, S., & Li, X. (2021). Complex event processing system for IoT greenhouse. In *E3S Web of Conferences, ICESCE* (Vol. 267, p. 01048). EDP Sciences.
9. Wang, Y. H., Cao, K., & Zhang, X. M. (2013). Complex event processing over distributed probabilistic event streams. *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, 66(10), 1808–1821.
10. Mekonnen, Y., Namuduri, S., Burton, L., Sarwat, A., & Bhansali, S. (2020). Review—Machine learning

- techniques in wireless sensor network based precision agriculture. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 167(3), 037522.
11. Robins, B. (2010). Complex event processing.
 12. Roldán, J., Boubeta-Puig, J., Martínez, J. L., & Ortiz, G. (2020). Integrating complex event processing and machine learning: An intelligent architecture for detecting IoT security attacks. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 149, 113251.
 13. Suhothayan, S., Narangoda, I. L., Chaturanga, S., Gajasinghe, K., Perera, S., & Nanayakkara, V. (2011, November). Siddhi: A second look at complex event processing architectures. In *Proceedings of the 2011 Gateway Computing Environments Workshop (GCE '11)*. IEEE.
 14. Roldan-Gomez, J., del Rincon, J. M., Boubeta-Puig, J., & Martinez, J. L. (2024). An automatic unsupervised complex event processing rules generation architecture for real-time IoT attacks detection. *Wireless Networks*, 30(6), 5127–5144.
 15. Patel, M., Rane, A., & Patni, V. (2024). Crop recommendation system using machine learning. In *Proceedings of the International Conference*.
 16. Rao, T. V. N., & Manasa, S. (2019). Artificial neural networks for soil quality and crop yield prediction using machine learning. *Future Revolution in Computer Science and Communication Engineering*, 5(1), 57–60.
 17. Xu, X., Gao, P., Zhu, X., Guo, W., Ding, J., Li, C., Zhu, M., & Wu, X. (2019). Design of an integrated climatic assessment indicator (ICAI) for wheat production: A case study in Jiangsu Province, China. *Ecological Indicators*, 101, 943–953.
 18. Sriram, K. P., Sujatha, P. K., Athinarayanan, S., Kanimozhi, G., & Joel, M. R. (2024). Transforming agriculture: A synergistic approach integrating topology with artificial intelligence and machine learning for sustainable and data-driven practice. In *Proceedings of the 2024 2nd International Conference on Sustainable Computing and Smart Systems (ICSCSS)* (pp. 1350–1354). IEEE.
 19. Mayer, C., Mayer, R., & Abdo, M. (2017). Grand challenge: StreamLearner – Distributed incremental machine learning on event streams. In *Proceedings of the 11th ACM International Conference on Distributed Event-Based Systems (DEBS '17)*. ACM.
 20. Sun, Y., Li, G., & Ning, B. (2020). Automatic rule updating based on machine learning in complex event processing. In *Proceedings of the 2020 IEEE 40th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS)* (pp. 1338–1343). IEEE.